

**INFLUENCE OF HOME ENVIRONMENT ON ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS A CASE STUDY
OF OYIGBO LGA OF RIVERS STATE**

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Abstract: The purpose of the study is to find out the influence of home background on the student's academic performance Oyigbo of Rivers State. The literature review was done through reading of textbooks newspapers and journals the method adopted were the questionnaires. The data got from the questionnaires were collected into figures and percentages which are show in tabular from. The responses from the data collected revealed that the socio-economic of the parents, residence and the size of the family affects the academic performance of students. Finally, recommendations to the above influence of home background on students academic performance Oyigbo LGA are made and some of that include the following. Parents should try as much as possible to give much affection and encouragement to their children in order, which their children would be motivated which could boost their academic performance parents should have the number of children that they can easily cater for early upbringing of a child plays a vital role in (later) education of the child.

Keyword: Influence, Home Environment, academic, performance, secondary school student, Oyigbo LG

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Though the learning environment provides a crucial role, it is important to acknowledge that a child's educational goals and overall growth are significantly influenced by their unique home circumstances. According to Eccles et al. (1998), several elements within the home environment, such as family funds and parental support, can significantly impact a child's likelihood of achieving success or experiencing failure. According to findings from studies conducted by the University of Minnesota Extension, there exists a positive correlation between academic success and a parent-child relationship that has been defined by caring, acceptance, and encouragement. Additionally, the responsiveness of parents to the needs they have for their children also plays a significant role in this correlation. There exists a negative association between parental overprotectiveness, authoritarianism, disapproval, and punishment and student learning. The education system

within a given society is shaped and adapted to align with the prevailing political and economic conditions of that society. Nigeria, as a developing nation, is actively engaged in the pursuit of educating its inhabitants in order to cultivate proficient personnel able to meet the demands of our fast changing global landscape. In line with this premise, multiple organizations have undertaken diverse policy strategies to ensure the effective implementation of education policies. The educational system has undergone a transition from the previous model inherited from colonial powers to the current 6-3-3-4 system. These efforts aim to develop an effective educational system that prioritises the achievement of high educational outcomes among students (James, 2008).

Nevertheless, it is perplexing to observe that although certain children exhibit commendable academic success, others struggle and exhibit subpar educational outcomes. When kids achieve achievement, there is no cause for concern; yet, when pupils experience failure, it raises concerns. Certain nations, such as Nigeria, have been marked by the presence of such deficiencies. The school administration and instructors' approach to instruction have frequently been subject to significant criticism. In this context, there is a limited number of individuals that demonstrate consideration towards additional issues that could potentially contribute to students' subpar academic achievements within educational institutions. The elements encompassed in this study involve the use and significance of the acquired materials, as well as the presence of cognitive impairments. Factors such as the age of the student, the climate in the classroom, and the background of the students' homes, among others, might have an impact on their academic performance. In this context, it is argued that the socio-economic background of a child has an impact on their academic performance. According to Bumpass (2009), background factors can include specific circumstances such as compromised physical health, emotional disruptions, and cognitive impairments. The socio-cultural context in which kids are raised significantly influences their self-perception and their perceptions of others.

Statement of the Problem

Generally, education is an endless process of enculturation, which begins from foundation (birth) and ends in grave. Statistics on academic performance of secondary school students has it that there has been a persistence poor performance of secondary school student. It has been proved by psychologists that difference in intelligence is not the only factors responsible for the difference in performance of students. There appears to be a prevalent lack of emphasis on the educational upbringing of children within the majority of households in our culture. It is evident that certain parents possess misconceptions regarding their children's academic achievement, as they lack awareness and fail to fulfil their responsibilities of providing advice and support in their child's educational endeavours. There is a prevailing belief among certain individuals that the collective success or failure of students in educational institutions can be attributed to the actions and effectiveness of instructors and school administrators. It is important to recognise that there are additional elements, beyond the talents of teachers, that might have an impact on the academic success of students, such as their home background. The home, as a fundamental institution for socialisation and the primary setting for children's learning, cannot be overlooked or excluded when examining the factors contributing to a child's low academic performance. The impact of a family's socio-economic condition on a child's academic success is acknowledged by certain individuals. Nevertheless, several studies have demonstrated that student performance is influenced by the collaborative efforts of both educational institutions and parents within various domestic settings.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study is aimed at examining the influence of home environment and parents' level of education on academic attainment of secondary school students in Oyibo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study aims to accomplish the following objectives:

1. To examine the combined impact of the home environment and parents' educational attainment on the academic performance of secondary school pupils in the Oyibo Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. To evaluate the correlation between the home environment and the academic achievement of secondary school pupils in the Oyibo Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. To Explore the influence of parent's level of education on academic performance of secondary school students in Oyibo Local Government Area of Rivers State
4. To investigate if academic performance of students in secondary school in Oyibo Local Government Area of Rivers State will differ in terms of gender.

Significance of the Study

The relevance for learning within a society is of utmost importance, and conducting a comprehensive analysis of students' academic performance holds great value for educational planners, teachers, government officials, and any other individuals or organisations invested in monitoring student progress. This study aims to investigate the acquisition of fundamental knowledge by parents, with the goal of establishing a strong educational foundation for their children and ultimately improving their academic performance. This phenomenon has emerged due to the home being the primary unit of socialisation. This study aims to assist parents in recognising the challenges associated with a disadvantaged home environment and acquiring strategies to improve their children's educational accomplishments. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights to educational planners regarding the influence of diverse household backgrounds on educational planning and administration, specifically in relation to individual differences. The guidance and counselling officer in the school can provide appropriate advice to students by possessing knowledge of their home background.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The scope of the study covers the influence of home environment on academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA of Rivers State. The researcher encountered some constraints and challenges which limited the scope of the study.

- a) **Availability of Research Material:** The research resources available to the researcher were sufficient, Consequently, this imposed a constraint on the investigation.
- b) **TIME:** The temporal constraints imposed on the study do not facilitate comprehensive coverage, as the researcher must integrate other scholarly commitments and examinations alongside the investigation.
- c) **Respondent Attitude:** The attitude of the respondent will be another challenge to be encountered by the researcher, many maybe un-cooperative.
- d) Apparently, research involves financial commitment beginning from its starting point to finishing point. They will be financial challenges in carrying out the research due to the prevailing unfriendly economic situation in Nigeria coupled with recession, where the research was carried out.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept “family”

The concept of family is often characterised as the most intimate and personal unit within social structures. The fundamental group holds significant importance as the smallest social unit within a given civilization. According to Odo (1990:10), the concept of family can be described as a social unit that resides together and engages in economic cooperation. The author posited that the foundation of family structures typically revolves around the union of one or more sexually cohabiting couples, with the common anticipation of procreation and subsequent assumption of parental duties by the adult members of the family. According to Ajila and Olutola (2007), the family is seen as the most intimate social institution due to the highly personal nature of the interactions and relationships among its members. The individual additionally expressed that a married couple lacking children, but being connected by strong personal bonds, does not meet the criteria for a family, as these kinds of bonds can potentially exist among partners who are not married. According to his perspective, the presence of children is what imparts a distinct character to a family. It is within such a familial context that an intimate and personal connection can be established, enabling the family to fulfil its essential roles of nurturing, safeguarding, and educating the children. Additionally, this familial unit serves as a conduit for the transmission of inherited social values and fosters a unique bond among all its members. The aforementioned family structure bears resemblance to the traditional Nigerian concept of family. According to conventional wisdom, it is commonly held that the presence of children solidifies the bond between a man and a woman, resulting in a durable and intimate relationship. The principal objective of this relationship is reproductive propagation. The concept of family can be categorised into two main forms: the nuclear family and the extended family. The nuclear family represents the fundamental structure of family organisation. The family unit consists of a father (husband), mother (wife), and their children.

The Concept “Home Background”

Home environment plays a significant influence in shaping a child's life. The concept of home environment encompasses the various elements, influences, and circumstances within the household that have an impact on the child's intellectual, behavioural, and psychological growth. These characteristics may encompass physical elements such as poverty, as well as psychological disorders arising from upbringing or social circumstances, such as feelings of emptiness and living in solitude. Additionally, broader cultural patterns of life associated with specific locations, such as suburban or metropolitan surroundings, may also contribute to these issues. According to Muola (2010), youngsters from diverse family backgrounds are subject to varying impacts due to these disparities, resulting in some youngsters possessing favourable home backgrounds while others have less advantageous ones. According to Fleege, as cited by Eke (1999), it has been observed that the background of certain individuals within families may exhibit temporal variations. The author additionally stated that parents, being the primary agents in constructing the family unit and exerting authority within it, bear the responsibility for shaping the nature of the domestic environment. Parenting attitudes play a crucial part in fostering a healthy home environment, wherein the adaptation of parents to culturally prescribed parenting responsibilities aligns with the evolving demands of the younger generation.

Theoretical Review

In order to ascertain the intellectual rigour of the research endeavour, it is imperative to incorporate a scientifically grounded theoretical framework that will serve as the foundation for a methodical examination.

Hence, the present study incorporates the use of the following theoretical frameworks: parental attachment theory, self-determination theory, and Maslow's motivational theory. The theory of parental attachment is a psychological framework that explores the emotional bond between parents and their children. It posits that the quality of this attachment has significant implications for the Bowlby (1980) introduced the concept of parental attachment theory. According to the theory, it is posited that during childhood, a kid develops a robust emotional attachment to a certain individual, commonly referred to as the carer, which thereafter has enduring implications throughout the individual's lifespan. According to the theoretician, the provision of delicate and touching available parenting is beneficial for the child's establishment of a secure attachment style, hence facilitating the child's socio-emotional development and overall well-being. Insufficiently sensitive and emotionally accessible parenting, or the neglect of a child's needs, can lead to the development of insecure attachment styles, which in turn serve as a risk factor for many mental health issues. The theory holds significance in the context of this study due to the proponent's provision of insights into the emotional development of children. Additionally, he provided practical recommendations for parents and guardians. Parents and guardians are increasingly recognising the importance of establishing a secure attachment bond with their children. These relationships will facilitate the development of safe attachment and a secure psychological state in children as they go into adulthood. Parents will acquire knowledge and comprehension regarding the biological and psychological need of their offspring, so enabling them to refrain from harbouring impractical anticipations regarding their children's behaviour. In this manner, parents may endeavour to circumvent the experience of frustration that arises when they have expectations that surpass the child's capacity.

Empirical Studies

This section provides a comprehensive evaluation of empirical studies conducted in areas relevant to the subject of inquiry. Baron and Byrne (1997) carried out a study examining the impact of home background on the academic performance of junior secondary school students in the Abeokuta South Local Government Area of Ogun State. The research methodology employed in this study was a survey approach, utilising a questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. The study used a sample size of 1000 pupils for research purposes. The data that was obtained underwent analysis utilising various statistical measures, including frequency tables, percentages, means, standard deviations, and t-tests. The study discovered, among various findings, that the socio-economic level of parents appreciably influences the academic performance of students. In a study conducted by Charles (2003), the focus was on investigating the correlation between the home background and the academic achievement of secondary school pupils in the Onitsha local government region of Anambra state. The study employed a correlational research design, with the primary data collection instrument being a questionnaire. The study's sample consisted of 450 pupils.

The acquired data were subjected to analysis utilising measures of central tendency such as the mean, as well as measures of variability such as the standard deviation. Additionally, the null hypotheses were assessed through the utilisation of regression analyses. The study's findings indicate that a majority of the students in high school within Anambra State are derived from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds, specifically within the lower 25 socio-economic families. However, these circumstances do not appear to have a detrimental impact on their academic attainment. The study additionally demonstrated that there is no significant correlation between family size and students' academic success. Nevertheless, the study revealed a noteworthy correlation between

the educational attainment of parents and the academic attainment of their children. The aforementioned study is relevant to the current study since both examine the home variables/factors that influence students' academic attainment. In a separate study, Chen and Lan (1998) performed research examining the impact of the family environment on the academic success of pupils in the Enugu East local government region of Enugu state. The study employed a survey design methodology. The study's sample included 240 students. The researcher employed a structured questionnaire as the instrument for data collection.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

In this chapter the research methodology used in the study is described. The settings where the study was conducted, the research design, the population/participants, the sampling techniques, the instruments used to collect the data, including methods implement to maintain validity and reliability of the instrument are described.

Research Design

This research was conducted using an Ex post facto design. A cross sectional survey method, which involves the use of questionnaire for the collection of data and also because the study aimed at examining how the independent variables (Home Environment) affects the dependent variable (Academic Performance), and also, it was used to determine a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables under study.

Sources of data collection

Data were collected from two main sources namely:

(i)Primary source and

(ii)Secondary source

Primary source:

These are materials of statistical investigation which were collected by the research for a particular purpose. They can be obtained through a survey, observation questionnaire or as experiment; the researcher has adopted the questionnaire method for this study.

Secondary source:

These are data from textbook Journal handset etc. they arise as byproducts of the same other purposes. Example administration, various other unpublished works and write ups were also used.

Population of the study

Population of a study is a group of persons or aggregate items, things the researcher is interested in getting information on the influence of home background on student's academic performance in secondary school. The population of this study is 1000 respondents consisted of students in eleven (11) secondary school in Oyigbo LGA.

Table 1 below shows the distribution of accessible population and the number in each school.

Table 1: Distributions of accessible population

S/N	Name of school	Samples
1	Community Secondary School	200
2	Oyigbo Government Secondary school	150
3	Springfield school	100
4	Ascender’s Christian school	100
5	Preston International School	100
6	Pacesetters Missionary School	85
7	Kings’ World International school	70
8	Mary Virginia International	65
9	Elnexus Secondary school	50
10	Wisdom Gate Secondary School	50
11	Capital International School	30
	Total	1000

Source: Research Data (2022)

Instrument

Academic performance rating Scale (APRS) by ChristopherMcGregory (2015)

The Academic performance Rating Scale (APRS) was developed by Christopher McGregor (2015). The instrument consists of eight items. The 4-point likert scale was used in rating thr responses.the response includes (i) Strongly Disagreed (ii) Disagree (iii) Agree (iv) Strongly Agree. The internal consistency of the scale is .89.

Sample and sampling procedure

Sampling technique or sampling is the process of selecting a group of individual from a population to study them and characterize the population as a whole, it also help researchers to infer information about a population based on results from a subset. It is important to select the right element of the sample. Therefore, the sampling technique that was used for this study is the purposive sampling technique and the convenience sampling technique, which is a type of non-probability sampling technique. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the setting, which are secondary schools in Oyigbo, while convenient sampling technique is used to access the sample of population of interest. Convenience sampling is used based on the availability and the willingness of individuals to participate in the study.

Sample size determination

Sample is the set people or items which constitute part of a given population sampling. Due to large size of the target population, to determine the sample size of the study, Taro Yamene’s formula was adopted as shown below:

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = Sample size sought

e = Level of significance usually 5% (0.05)

N = Population size

Thus, to calculate the sample size will be,

$$N \frac{1000}{1+1000(0.05)^2} = 286$$

Based on how the questionnaire was distributed, the individual sampling techniques was used. The Bowley's (1994) formula is;

$$nh = N = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

Where: nh= the number allocated to each emporium to be computed.

n = the population size purposively selected

Nh = number of students

Computations become.

Table 2: Unit Sample Size Computation

Name of school	Strength	Unit	Sample	Unit	Sample
	Responses	Calculation	Size		
Community Secondary School	200	286 x 200/1000	57		
Oyigbo Government Secondary school	150	286 x 150/1000	43		
Springfield school	100	286 x 100/1000	29		
Ascender's Christian school	100	286 x 100/1000	29		
Preston International School	100	286 x 100/1000	29		
Pacesetters Missionary School	85	286 x 85/1000	24		
Kings' World International school	70	286 x 70/1000	20		
Mary Virginia International	65	286 x 65/1000	19		
Elnexus Secondary school	50	286 x 50/1000	14		
Wisdom Gate Secondary School	50	286 x 50/1000	14		
Capital International School	30	286 x 30/1000	8		
Total	1000		286		

Source: Field Data (2022)

Instrument for data collection

The major research instrument used is the questionnaires. This was appropriately moderated. The secretaries were administered with the questionnaires to complete, with or without disclosing their identities. The questionnaire was designed to obtain sufficient and relevant information from the respondents. The primary

data contained information extracted from the questionnaires in which the respondents were required to give specific answer to a question by ticking in front of an appropriate answer and administered the same on staff of the two organizations: The questionnaires contained structured questions which were divided into sections A and B.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter dealt with the presentation of data, analysis of data, interpretation of data, a summary of findings and discussion of findings.

Demographic Information

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	499	54.0
Female	429	46.0
Age		
10-12years	292	32.0
13-15years	362	39.0
16-18years	274	30.0
Parents Educational Qualification		
First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC)	124	13.0
First Degree	393	42.0
Master's Degree	262	28.0
PhD	149	17.0
Parent's Occupation		
Employed	235	25.0
Unemployed	202	22.0
Skilled Labourer	228	28.0
Business/Trade	228	25.0
Total	150	100.0

Researchers Fieldwork, 2023

Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the joint influence of home environment and parents' level of education on the academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA?

Table 4: Model Summary of Home Environment and Parents Educational Qualification on Academic Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.692	.479	.476	2.54537

Table 4 shows the result of the analysis of the research question carried out to determine the joint influence of home environment and parents' level of education on the academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA. The table shows an R-value of 0.692, R² value of 0.479 and an Adjusted R² value of 0.476. From

the above-stated result home environment and parents' level of education accounted for 47.6% of the variation observed in academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA

Research Question Two: What is the influence of home environment on the academic performance of secondary school students Oyigbo LGA

Table 5: Model Summary of Home Environment on Academic Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.608	.370	.370	2.79278

Table 5 shows the result of the analysis of the research question carried out to determine the influence of home environment on the academic performance of secondary school students Oyigbo LGA. The table shows an R-value of 0.608, R² value of 0.370 and an Adjusted R² value of 0.370. From the above-stated result there is a strong positive relationship between home environment and academic performance. The result also shows that home environment is responsible for 37% of the observed variation in academic performance in Oyigbo LGA

Research Question Three: Parents level of education does not influence academic performance of male students in secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA?

Table 6: Model Summary of Parents Level of Education on Academic Performance (Male)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.651	.424	.421	2.68748

Table 6 shows the result of the analysis of the research question carried out to determine if parents' level of education influences the academic performance of male students in secondary school in Oyigbo LGA. The table shows an R-value of 0.651, R² value of 0.424 and an Adjusted R² value of 0.421. From the above-stated result there is a strong positive relationship between parent's level of education and academic performance of male students. The result also shows that parent's level of education is responsible for 42.1% of the observed variation in academic performance of male students in secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA

The academic performance of students in Oyigbo LGA does not differ based on the parent's educational qualification?

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Discussion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of home environment on academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis one states that home environment and parents' level of education do not have joint influence on academic performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo LGA of Rivers State The result obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis one showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The result of this finding is in line with Chevalier, Harmon, Sullivan, & Walker (2005) who were of the view that only parents' educational level is not responsible for students' educational performances but home investment and socio-

economic status of the family is also contributing. Educated parents were found good in educational decisions of their children. The large co-relation among parent's involvement in school and subject selection were estimated. Azhar, Nadeem, Naz, Perveen, & Samreen, (2013) and Jerrim (2009) also supported the findings of the study that parents' educational level and decisions regarding students schooling have close positive co-relation. Home environment and educational facilities for children also make a significant difference in the performances of students in their academics. As Harb and El-Shaarawi (2006) identified that school and subject selection decisions along with academic freedom do have a positive impact on the academic lives of students. Hypothesis two which stated that Home environment does not significantly influence the academic performance of secondary school students Oyigbo LGA of Rivers State. The result shows that Home environment significantly influence the academic performance of secondary school students Oyigbo LGA of Rivers State. The result obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis one showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. This hypothesis revealed that home environment has a significant influence on students' academic performance. The findings is in line with that of Anene (2005) who investigated the influence of home environment on student's academic performance in Kitui West sub-county, Kenya. The study sought to determine the influence of parents' socio-economic status on students' academic performance. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample of 8 principals in 8 schools, out of 28 public secondary schools, 8 PTA chairpersons in 8 selected schools out of 28 and 144 students, out of population 1440 students. Questionnaires were used for data collection. The findings of the study were that the home environment influences students' academic performance ($r = 0.8$), parents'/ family involvement influence students' academic performance in public secondary schools ($r = 0.05$).

The third hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between parent level of education and academic performance of students in secondary schools Oyigbo Local Government. The result obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis three showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. This hypothesis revealed that the performance of highly educated parents' children was found good as compared to less educated parents, meaning that parents level of education has a positive relationship on academic performance, which implies that the higher level of education of parents, the better the performance of secondary school students in Oyigbo Local Government Area. This is in line with Haris and Goodall (2008) revealed in their studies that highly educated parents concentrate on the text enriched environment at home. Further, they have the experience of student life extensively, so they are aware of the problems are its appropriate solutions. Their guiding and motivational approach towards their children contributes positively in their academic achievement. The children of intermediate and above showed 90% results as compared to 56% of less educated parents' children. Jerrim (2009) supported that the intergenerational influences are apparent and can be easily studied in children educational attainments.

Hypothesis four which states that academic performance of students in Oyigbo LGA does not differ significantly based on gender of students. The result obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypotheses four showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that students' academic performance differed based on gender. This means that male students had better academic performance than female students. The results of this study seem to be contrary to the findings of some of the previous studies such as Orabi (2007), Dayioglu & Turut (2007), Khwaileh & Zaza (2010) who have identified significant gender differences

in the academic performance of students' especially female students outperforming their male counterparts. Meanwhile, the results supports the findings of some other scholars like Wangu (2014) who claimed that male students outperform their female counterparts and Goni et al. (2015) who claimed that there is no such significant gender difference in student's academic performance.

Conclusion

Conclusion Based on the findings of this study, it is therefore concluded that to improve the performance of both male and female students, all genders need to be provided with equal opportunities in the learning environment. There is need to avail more teaching and learning resources.

On the issue of parental educational level, it was concluded that the level of education of parents had an impact on their children's academic performance. It was also concluded that the educational level of parent had a consistent direct relationship on the children's cognitive and behavioral outcomes. On family financial situation it was concluded that there is a direct relationship between parental financial and human capital on the successful learning experience of their children and their academic success and equally low income of parents had a negative academic performance expectation on their children. On matters of family size, it was concluded that in most big families the size of the family had a moderate relationship with the academic performance of their children but on the other hand it was revealed that children from large families were found to perform poorly in schools than children from small families.

Recommendation

In view of the findings discussed in this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Home environment is the most significant factor affecting student's academic achievement. There are various factors in home environment which are lacking in our homes for our children, which has a negative impact and a low correlation with students' academic achievement. Therefore, it is recommended that students should be provide a serene home environment for studies which could help to promote student's overall development. The most suitable mean is to give proper time to children, and an educative environment at home. Family member's interactions at home are great source of development for children. It provides a source for the social and intellectual development of children. It also enhances children confidence level. It is therefore recommended that students should be exposed to inner interactions of family; they should be allowed to express their view point on different family matters and might be treated as a functional member of the family.
2. Government should make adequate funding into education system such that would cater for the less privileged by providing academic materials including relevant and current textbooks that could enhance students' academic performance. Philanthropists are also encouraged to give more financial and material supports to education in order to academic performance of the students in Nigerian secondary schools.
3. Parents should be sensitized on the need to raise small families in order to enable them provide for their educational needs that will motivate the children to learn effectively and perform satisfactorily in their academic. □
4. The government should also embark on a mass enlightenment campaign to educate the parents more on the importance of education. And parents should endeavor to be also academically sound if they must influence their children's academic performance.

5. Government should also improve on the socio-economic welfare of her citizenry as this will go a long way in raising the living standards of its people which will to a large extent impact on the income level of parents who will earn more in order to support the welfare of their children in schools.
6. Perception about home environment and academic achievement in gender. Henceforth, this present paper recommends that it is very significant for the parents at home to develop an environment of self-understanding of their feelings, emotions and sentiments in order to transmute that thoughtfulness and understanding in the children. It is fact that the more the parents and guardians are capable to comprehend their feelings and emotions, the better they would be capable to manage their kids' emotional and intellectual personality. Therefore, home environment plays significant role in emotional and thoughtful competence or incompetence of parents and guardians has confirmatory or hostile effects on teenagers. Findings of this research indicated that children raised in loving, caring, secure, consistent and stable home environment have a greater probability of developing well in socially, psychologically, physically, emotionally and morally
7. The study recommends that government, curriculum planners and examination bodies in policy making and in planning educational strategies to reconsider the influence of home environment on academic performance for the study area.
8. Illiterate parents should be encouraged to go to school, in that their literacy will enhance their children academic achievement in schools.

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